

ANNUAL PROGRESS REPORT ●

1 November 2024 - 31 December 2025

Introduction

In October 2024, a group of dedicated oceanographers, fisheries science experts, NGO and government representatives, and private sector practitioners met at the University of New South Wales, Sydney, to officially formalize the [Fishing Vessel Ocean Observing Network \(FVON\)](#). This meeting culminated in an international Steering Committee representing seven countries and 10 fishing-vessel-based ocean observing programs, some consisting of hundreds of vessels and others in operation for over two decades. Since then, FVON has expanded to include several working groups as well as a broader Member Committee leading pilots, representing industry, and lending expertise. The community is eager, passionate, and continuing to grow.

The Steering Committee is dedicated to the mission that *FVON is a global network that collaboratively collects rigorous, cost-effective ocean data with end-users, driving a transformative shift in our understanding of the changing ocean and informing sustainable decision-making*. Since its inception, FVON has been working toward a series of [strategic pillars](#) that will enable this vision, in alignment with broader international standards such as [OCG maturity metrics](#).

This report evaluates progress and delays against each of these metrics over the period from 1 November 2024 to 31 December 2025. To do so, the FVON Secretariat integrated a combination of select Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and self-assessments from FVON working group chairs in line with FVON and OCG metrics. In doing so, this report will indicate strategic objectives for the annual period of 1 January 2026 to 31 December 2026 and better enable FVON to achieve its mission.

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Executive Summary

In 2025, FVON transformed from a loose consortium of programs to a coordinated international observing network with defined governance, identity, and strategic pillars. Building on its formalization in late 2024, the interdisciplinary Steering Committee brought together expertise from long-standing observing programs (such as eMOLT and AdriFOOS) with more recent but rapidly expanding projects (such as FishSOOP and SFiN), while supporting emerging pilots in under-observed regions of the world such as the Pacific Islands, The Bahamas, Tanzania, and Mexico. Simultaneously, additional conversations with stakeholders in Thailand, southern Africa, and several nations in the Caribbean developed, advancing toward new pilots in these emerging regions. This progress has planted FVON as a leader within the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) for its scalability and capacity to serve underrepresented regions of the world and diverse stakeholder communities.

744 VESSELS	255 NEW VESSELS	70,000+ CASTS	7 NEW COUNTRIES	15 ACTIVE COUNTRIES
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Institutionally, 2025 marked significant maturation. FVON now meets or exceeds baseline expectations across several Observations Coordination Group (OCG) attributes and is firmly “mature” in several domains, including community of practice, mission clarity, innovation mechanisms, and capacity development engagement. Approximately 29% of “casts”—data collected up and down a water column, along with, if applicable, the seabed floor—are delivered to the Global Telecommunication System (GTS), contributing directly to global forecasting systems, and FVON maintains active engagement with

[OceanOPS](#) on metadata standards with established interoperable data pathways through several repositories.

Simultaneously, the creation of a formal governance structure enabled FVON to make substantial progress against its newly defined strategy in a structured manner.

- The **Sensor Intercomparison Study Task Team** completed Phase 1 testing, which included both quantitative analysis of sensor performance against reference CTDs as well as qualitative assessment of best practices for use aboard vessels by fishing crews.
- The **Data Management Subcommittee** produced a GitHub identifying QC flags in use across FVON programs for unification, while also leading the broader OceanOPS Passport effort.
- The **Financial Innovation Subcommittee** led grant proposals and developed a strategy toward sustained ocean observing along with a proposed business model that integrates input from a series of stakeholder interviews.
- The **Secretariat** led the dissemination of monthly newsletters, co-design workshops for new pilots, a two-part FVON webinar series, and the creation of short films and other media for FVON's communications channels.
- The **Steering Committee** met monthly and presented at conferences, published papers, and engaged in critical international discussions to increase FVON's global influence.
- The **Member Committee** led regional FVON programs, engaged with local fishing communities, established connections with national institutions, and offered broad technical input on various workstreams.

However, despite this significant progress, several pillars of FVON's mission remain to be developed. Established, unified best practices are a key characteristic of a mature network, ensuring quality data under FAIR and CARE standards and broad interoperability. FVON faces unique complexities for standardizing across the entire network due to the diversity of the fishing industry around the world, making this objective particularly challenging. Meanwhile, because FVON is more accessible for non-traditional stakeholders in nations with limited resources, capacity building is highly relevant. FVON has a responsibility to ensure that program participants can engage with the scientific applications of the data and communicate end use demands, supporting program longevity. While FVON hosts workshops, creates communications projects, and teaches fishers how to use equipment and access data, a dedicated Capacity Building Subcommittee is necessary to institutionalize these procedures. Additionally, while FVON's geographic reach expanded significantly in 2025, representation gaps in its leadership remain in South America, parts of Asia, and Africa.

Meanwhile, many of the achievements of 2025 were made possible through in-kind contributions or a collection of short-term philanthropic grants. Uncertainty around Secretariat support beyond July 2026 remains a key threat to core operational activities. FVON's preliminary research into the governance structures of other OCG networks indicated that heavy reliance on voluntary contributions created difficulties in sustaining and scaling observations, leading FVON to investigate alternative revenue mechanisms. The Financial Innovation Subcommittee's proposed business model seeks to generate sustainable revenue for FVON coordination and data collection efforts, but its implementation is at a halt until FVON can 1) establish a legal institution and 2) decide on endorsement criteria for service providers that are informed by unified FVON QA and QC standards. These objectives are therefore of the highest priority for the coming year, when transitioning from 2025 as a foundational year of institutional groundwork to 2026: a year of converting expansion momentum into durable, standardized, and globally recognized fishing vessel ocean observing capacity.

Key Performance Indicators

Program Metrics

With thanks to the Data Management Subcommittee, certain Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are now available for data served through the [FVON ERDDAP](#), but tracking metrics across all diverse FVON programs and pilots remains challenging without mandatory or automated reporting (a star* indicates where metrics are not exact).

Reference Period: 1 November 2024 – 31 December 2025

Cast: Includes data collected up and down a water column along with the seabed floor (if applicable).

Vessel: One data collection platform, which may include multiple instruments.

GTS: The Global Telecommunication System, managed by the World Meteorological Organization for global forecasting purposes.

FVON Operator	Vessels	New Vessels	Casts	Casts to GTS
eMOLT <i>Northeast USA</i>	142	103 +264%	19,967	7,613 38%
ODN <i>Bangladesh, Ghana, Mexico, Tanzania, The Bahamas, USA</i>	78	54 +225%	10,351	7,723 75%
SFiN <i>Japan</i>	332	31 +10%	13,397*	0
AMOS <i>New Zealand</i>	106	17 +19%	10,746	1,000* 9%
FishSOOP <i>Australia, Fiji, French Polynesia, Papua New Guinea, Samoa, Solomon Islands</i>	83	50 +152%	15,781*	4,014 25%
AdriFOOS <i>Italy</i>	3	0	1,033	0
TOTALS	744	255 +52%	71,275	20,350 29%

NOTE: Some of the casts that are not sent to the GTS are publicly available through other access points in delayed mode (due to privacy concerns of the data collectors).

To achieve 10,000 vessels by 2030, FVON must expand by roughly 68% each year, assuming exponential growth from 2026.

- 2026** 1,250 vessels (506 new)
- 2027** 2,100 vessels (850 new)
- 2028** 3,528 vessels (1,428 new)
- 2029** 5,927 vessels (2,399 new)
- 2030** 10,000 vessels (4,073 new)

Network Scale

Metric	Number	Description
Total active countries	15	Australia, Bangladesh, Fiji, French Polynesia (France), Ghana, Italy, Japan, Mexico, New Zealand, Papua New Guinea, Samoa, Solomon Islands, Tanzania, The Bahamas, United States of America
Total new countries	7	Bangladesh, Fiji, French Polynesia, Mexico, Papua New Guinea, Samoa, Solomon Islands
Expansion by countries	78%	Growth from 9 (2024) to 15 (2025) countries.
Expansion by vessels	52%	Growth from 489 (2024) to 744 (2025) vessels.
Coverage of IOC member states	10%	IOC Member States (152)
Presence in ocean basins	4	Atlantic, Indian, Pacific, Southern
Total active pilot sites <i>2- years of operation funded</i>	6	ODN: Baja California Sur, Bangladesh, FVON-Bahamas, Ghana, OceanObserve-TZ, Oceanography On Deck
Total active programs	7	AdriFOOS, AMOS (Moana Project), BDC (ODN), eMOLT, FishSOOP, PI-FVON, SFiN

NOTE: Regional metrics correspond to the Exclusive Economic Zones where data is collected, not the nationality of the data collection platform.

Data Uptake and Impact

Metric	Number	Description
Percentage of casts to the GTS	29%	AMOS, eMOLT, ODN, FishSOOP
Data availability*	-	<p>AdriFOOS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delayed-mode temperature (2012-2020), metadata, and ERDDAP Delayed-mode temperature metadata (2021) Delayed-mode temperature DO chlorophyll-a (2023-2025), ERDDAP, and EMODnet visualizations <p>AMOS: AMOS THREDDS</p> <p>eMOLT/ODN: FVON ERDDAP</p> <p>FishSOOP: AODN</p>
Presence at conferences and events in 2025	14*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SOT-13 OCG-16 International Conference on AI for the Oceans Earthx2025

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EGU25 • Our Ocean Conference 2025 • NAUTILOS Final Conference on Advancing the Democratisation of Ocean Science • One Ocean Science Congress • Blue Economy Finance Forum • 2025 UN Ocean Conference • ICES ASC 2025 • Climate Week NYC • Dialogues with Industry: Ocean Observing of the Future, parts 1-3 • GCFI 78 • Observing the Future workshop
Scientific publications in 2025	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IMOS Fishing Vessels as Ships of Opportunity (FishSOOP), Real-time Quality Assurance and Quality Control Practice Manual, Version 1.0 • D7.2 – Fisheries and Aquaculture Observing Systems demonstration final report • Advancing Observations of Western Boundary Currents: Integrating Novel Technologies for a Coordinated Monitoring Approach • Fishing for Ocean Data in the East Australian Current • Positive data circulation established by Kyushu Smart Fisheries (QSF) team

Communications

Metric	Number	Description
News coverage in 2025	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GOOS Status Report 2025 • Collaborating with commercial tuna fishing vessels as Ships of Opportunity to collect essential ocean variable data • In the Caribbean, fishermen are helping to predict the next big hurricane • Fishers and researchers are working together to create a 'transformational' data set • Our Ocean, Our Action: See You in Busan! • From hundreds to tens of thousands: FVON commits to an ocean data revolution • Innovations in the Marine Economy – Innovation in Data (Season 4 Episode 6) • How Fishers Are Protecting Their Communities from Hurricanes
Short films and documentaries in 2025	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Pacific Fishing Vessel Observing Network Boosts Climate Science • Catching Data: How Bahamian fishers help forecast stronger storms

Workshops, webinars, and events in 2025		4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ocean Data for Sustainable & Profitable Fisheries Part I & Ocean Data for Sustainable & Profitable Fisheries Part 2 (316 attendees) • North Atlantic Arc Workshop report (44 attendees) • Sustaining Ocean Observations to Support Hurricane Readiness in The Bahamas: A Roadmap • EDF-Mexico workshop: Baja Technology Testbed
FVON newsletter	Total external newsletters in 2025	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • November 2025 • October 2025 • September 2025 • August 2025 • July 2025 • June 2025 • May 2025 • April 2025
	Mailing list recipients	88	Including 35 external mailing list sign-ups from the FVON website.
LinkedIn	Total followers	550	Grown from 0 (2024).
	Total posts	45	~5 posts per month (April-December)
	Total impressions	27,000+	~850 impressions per post

Inclusivity

Metric	Number	Description
Steering Committee (SC) membership	12	A. Miguel Santos, Christopher Cusack, Cooper Van Vranken, George Maynard, Hassan Moustahfid, João de Souza, Julie Jakoboski, Michela Martinelli, Moninya Roughan, Patrick Gorringer, Peter McComb, Shin Kida
SC representation by country of residence	7	Australia, Italy, Japan, New Zealand, Portugal, Sweden, United States of America
Member Committee (MC) membership	32	Ainhoa Caballero, Andrew Corso, Antonio Novellino, Bipendra Prakash, Brandon Bethel, Carles Castro Muniain, Caroline Cusack, César González-Pola, Cynthia Wickham, Drew Wright, Enrico Cecapolli, Filipe Nhanquê, Fiona Carse, Hellen Kizenga, Jerome Aucan, Julie Duchêne, Kwame Agyekum, Lancelot Blondeel, Linus Stoltz, Max Tukana, Mbiru Moses Mapombe, Nick Hirose, Pierluigi Penna, R. Venkat, Simon Nicol, Stella Caon, Tanuspong (Men) Pokavanich, Terry McConnell, Tetsutaro Takikawa, Véronique Lago, Z. Aleck Wang, Zac Anderson

MC representation by country of residence	17	Australia, Belgium, Fiji, France, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, India, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Solomon Islands, Spain, Tanzania, Thailand, The Bahamas, United Kingdom, United States of America
FVON working groups	5	Data Management Subcommittee, Financial Innovation Subcommittee, Sensor Intercomparison Study Task Team, Secretariat
Working group membership	26	George Maynard, Carles Castro Muniain, Véronique Lago, Chris Cusack, Peter McComb, Moninya Roughan, Cooper Van Vranken, Dustin Colson Leaning, Aubrey Taylor, Michela Martinelli, Shin Kida, Tetsutaro Takikawa, Nick Hirose, Enrico Cecapolli, Lorenzo Zacchetti, Emilie Breviere, Linus Stoltz, Zac Anderson, João Souza, Julie Jakoboski, Pierluigi Penna, Irena Draca, Patrick Gorringer, Miguel Santos, Rita Esteves, Matt Irwin
Working group representation by country of residence	8	United States of America, Spain, Australia, New Zealand, Italy, Japan, Sweden, Portugal
Geographic distribution of vessels	-	<p>The pie chart illustrates the geographic distribution of vessels. Japan is the largest segment, followed by the United States of America, New Zealand, Australia, and The Bahamas. Mexico is also represented by a small segment.</p>

Strategic Implications

- Establish a central, automated system for tracking KPIs across all FVON programs for internal coordination.
- In 2025, FVON expanded by roughly 52% in comparison to the 68% goal even though many individual programs (eMOLT, ODN, FishSOOP) are expanding at a greater rate. Continue sustaining existing efforts while prioritizing expansion via new pilots and programs in 2026.
- Scientific attendance at conferences was strong, but FVON could focus on publishing more papers relating to ocean modeling, fisheries management, and early warning systems.
- Communications projects were consistent and numerous throughout the year, following the creation of the FVON logo, branding, and website. Partner amplification (particularly with GOOS and SAFET) significantly helped build out FVON communications. On LinkedIn, document posts (highest engagement rates) are best for reports and webinars. Image posts are best for reach

and repost performance when running features on places or people. Reels are best shared on Instagram for audience expansion. Twitter and Facebook are light-touch amplification tools.

- The MC has broad geographic diversity across North America, Europe, Africa, and Oceania, but lacks representation in South America and parts of Asia. The SC only consists of members from Europe, Japan, Australia, and the USA. FVON should prioritize the geographic diversity of its leadership in 2026.

Status Against OCG Maturity Metrics

OCG attributes are currently under review and subject to change. Some metrics do not include an “advanced” standard. Additionally, certain metrics are not verified across all FVON programs (a star* indicates uncertainty). However, these metrics provide a helpful reference for evaluating FVON’s progress against OCG priorities.

Maturity Metric	Status	Criteria
1: Global in scale	2024 MATURE	BASELINE Presence in 1 ocean basin OR 10% of IOC member states . ADVANCED Presence in 2 ocean basins OR 30% of IOC member states.
	2025 MATURE	MATURE Presence in 4 ocean basins OR 70% of IOC member states.
2: Observes one or more EOY or ECV	2024 BASELINE	BASELINE Observes one or more EOYs/ECVs.
	2025 MATURE	MATURE Has mechanisms in place for considering the addition of more EOYs/ECVs.
3: Observations are sustained	2024 N/A	BASELINE 20% of vessels are on sustained funding (4+ cycles).
	2025 N/A	ADVANCED 50% of vessels are on sustained funding. MATURE 90% of vessels are on sustained funding.
4: Community of practice	2024 EMERGING	BASELINE Has a Steering Committee with TORs that has met at least once.
	2025 MATURE	ADVANCED Steering Committee meets every two years. MATURE Steering Committee meets every year.
5: Maintains network mission and targets	2024 EMERGING	BASELINE Has identified its unique contribution to GOOS and has defined OCG network-relevant targets.

	2025 EMERGING	MATURE Reports to OCG on network target performance and regularly considers whether it continues to supply unique observations to GOOS that are not available via newer methods.
6: Delivers data that are free, open, and available in a timely manner	2024 BASELINE	BASELINE 10% of real-time OR delayed-mode data is delivered to the GTS/OceanOPS. ADVANCED 50% of real-time OR delayed-mode data is delivered to the GTS/OceanOPS.
	2025 BASELINE	MATURE 90% of real-time OR delayed-mode data is delivered to the GTS/OceanOPS.
7: Ensures metadata quality and delivery	2024 N/A	BASELINE 10% of data flows with metadata of sufficient quality as set by the OceanOPS Passport. ADVANCED 50% of data flows with metadata of sufficient quality as set by the OceanOPS Passport.
	2025 N/A	MATURE 90% of data flows with metadata of sufficient quality as set by the OceanOPS Passport.
8: Develops and follows standards and best practices	2024 EMERGING	BASELINE 20% of EOVs observed are covered by maintained and accessible GOOS-endorsed best practices. ADVANCED 50% of EOVs observed are covered by maintained and accessible GOOS-endorsed best practices.
	2025 EMERGING	MATURE 90% of EOVs observed are covered by maintained and accessible GOOS-endorsed best practices.
9: Undertakes capacity development and technology transfer	2024 EMERGING	BASELINE Considers capacity development processes in network strategy. MATURE Develops or engages in activities that enable new communities of ocean observers, supports diversity and inclusivity in its members, and engages with ECOPs.
	2025 MATURE	

10: Environmental stewardship awareness	2024 BASELINE	BASELINE Considers the environmental impact of the network.
	2025 BASELINE	MATURE Actively engages in appropriate environmental stewardship actions, considering materials and demonstrating value outweighing impact.
11: Innovation and private sector collaboration	2024 EMERGING	BASELINE Considers pathways for assessing new technologies or other relevant innovations.
	2025 MATURE	MATURE Has a mechanism to consider new technologies or other relevant innovations and has a mechanism or focal point in its governance structure for private sector collaboration.

Strategic Implications

- Scale geographically across a greater number of IOC member states in addition to maintaining a presence across multiple ocean basins. (1)
- Continue conducting instrument intercomparison studies and evaluate the incorporation of more EOVs in observing efforts. (2)
- Improve KPI tracking to better understand the financial sustainability of FVON programs. (3)
- Continue monthly Steering Committee meetings with clear reporting and outputs. (4)
- Improve OCG reporting and tracking to better understand FVON progress against other OCG networks. (5)
- Encourage all existing and new FVON programs to deliver data to the GTS. (6)
- Remain engaged in the Metadata Passport Task Team and incorporate new guidelines into unified FVON standards. (7)
- Prioritize the development of FVON-wide best practices for GOOS endorsement. (8)
- Continue expanding diverse representation across all levels of FVON, sharing knowledge, and leading capacity development workshops. (9)
- Evaluate the environmental impact of coordination and leadership activities and propose strategies to lower FVON's overall emissions. (10)
- Continue Financial Innovation activities and increase engagement with the private sector. (11)

Status Against FVON's Strategic Pillars

Pillar 1: Quality Data

Pillar Description	Governance
FVON fosters a paradigm shift in the availability of rigorous, high-quality data, ensuring equitable access at scale while adhering to CARE and FAIR data practices.	Data Management Subcommittee Sensor Intercomparison Study Task Team Best Practices Subcommittee (TBD)
Key Achievements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance: Established Data Management Subcommittee and Sensor Intercomparison Study Task Team with defined scopes and objectives. • Stakeholder Engagement: Developed a strategy to engage instrument companies, with regular communications and feedback throughout the course of the sensor study. • Quality Assurance: Completed a review of instruments in use across FVON and commercially available. Defined a common protocol and data analysis framework for testing sensors. Conducted three campaigns, documented in the Phase 1 cruise report. • Quality Control: FVON GitHub created, advancing QC flag unification across programs. Starting point established from OBPS-endorsed IMOS best practices. • Metadata and Interoperability: Metadata standards (structure, fields, and shared expectations) are under development. FVON leads progress on the OceanOPS Metadata Passport. More WMO IDs were obtained for relevant platforms and deployments. • Data Sharing: FVON ERDDAP instance deployed with data from several programs. Progress made on the FVON data portal, including improvements to access, visibility, and usability. 	
Gaps and Challenges	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance: U.S. government shutdown created external delays and uncertainty. Lack of funding for work activities limited progress to the in-kind capacity and resources of the working members and goodwill of sensor manufacturers. Need for clarification between QA and QC ownership and responsibilities. • Stakeholder Engagement: General limitations in the availability of robust, low-cost sensors fit for fishing gear to collect parameters other than temperature. • Quality Assurance: Limited ship time and in-kind support impacted the ability to comply with defined test protocols, extending the data analysis phase. • Quality Control: Challenges in building consensus across a diverse group. 	

- **Data Sharing:** Decision-making is ongoing across FVON around how data is shared, when, and under what terms.

Pillar 2: Mutual Benefits

Pillar Description	Governance
FVON maximizes the value of ocean data for users and fishing industry observer-users, ensuring direct benefits for those who collect and use the data while enabling the sustainable management of the blue economy.	Data Modeling Subcommittee (TBD)
Key Achievements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry Benefits: New data tools developed by IMOS, Oceanum, and ODN for use by fishers. Publication on the economic value of data used by the SFiN fishing industry, incorporating fisher testimonies. Numerous communications materials highlighting fisher and coastal community benefits (webinar series, short films, blogs). • Scientific Benefits: Several publications, including model improvements in the Western Boundary Current. • Political Benefits: Significant interest from national delegates in Mexico and other countries in the Caribbean to implement FVON following presentations at CoastPredict and IOCARIBE events. More interest growing from Canada, India, Thailand, and Africa. Strong leadership from Canada, Iceland, the Faroes, the UK, and Ireland in co-designing the North Atlantic Arc. • Stakeholder Engagement: Co-design workshops held in Mexico, The Bahamas, Tanzania, and the North Atlantic (with over 30 participating institutions) aligned stakeholder interests for maximum data impact. FVON service providers engaged through the sensor study and through Financial Innovation interviews. 	
Gaps and Challenges	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry Benefits: There remain limited publications on the impact of ocean data in the private sector. Some fishers receive stipends for participating. • Scientific Benefits: U.S. shutdown and bureaucratic challenges are delaying analysis of FVON data impacts on hurricane forecasting in The Bahamas. • Political Benefits: Demonstrated scientific and economic improvements are not yet translating into policy recommendations at the national or international level. • Stakeholder Engagement: Despite private sector outreach, there remains limited participation from blue economy industries during FVON co-design workshops. 	

Pillar 3: Global Advocacy

Pillar Description	Governance
Through strategic engagement and communication, FVON amplifies stakeholders' understanding of the link between ocean data collection and human impact and advocates for meaningful change.	Secretariat

Key Achievements
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance: Communications Plan drafted and ratified. Secretariat established to execute the communications plan, among other activities. • Communications Channels: FVON logo and brand guide established. New FVON website launched, including case studies of individual program benefits. Newsletters released monthly throughout the year. Active LinkedIn, Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook accounts with high-quality engagement on LinkedIn and effective partner amplification. • Projects: Two-part webinar series co-hosted by SAFET and GOOS and attended by 316 participants, responsible for peaking LinkedIn impressions (9,318 on 1 October) and new followers (19 on 6 October). Testimonies from fishers recorded and applied in new films (The Bahamas, the Pacific Islands), blogs, social media posts, and newsletters.
Gaps and Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance: Communications progress is threatened by reduced Secretariat capacity at the end of July 2026. • Communications Channels: Posting cadence largely depends on Secretariat capacity, which fluctuates heavily. There are relatively low returns on social media, which requires further development. Engagement lacks diversity and is largely linked to other ocean observing networks and a scientific audience. • Projects: Capacity for multiple communications projects in one year is limited, despite the success of the FVON webinar series and hosted events. Development of media is largely dependent on EDF in-kind contributions and/or grant funding.

Pillar 4: Inclusivity

Pillar Description	Governance
FVON ensures equitable access to ocean data collection and its benefits, empowering all stakeholders to contribute and benefit.	Capacity Building Subcommittee (TBD)
Key Achievements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance: Targeted discussions around capacity building with OCG leadership. Significant ECOP representation. Expansion of the Member Committee to include program leads in Ghana, Tanzania, The Bahamas, and the Solomon Islands. Presentations to the Steering Committee from program leads in Thailand and the Solomon Islands. • Expansion in Key Regions: Expansion of FVON in Tanzania and The Bahamas. Establishment of FVON in Mexico, Fiji, Samoa, French Polynesia, the Solomon Islands, and Papua New Guinea. (Additional expansions: Alaska, Northeast United States, Australia.) • Knowledge Sharing: Workshops held in Mexico, The Bahamas, Tanzania, and the North Atlantic (virtual) to build scientific expertise and expand pilot ownership. • Sustainability: Development of a long-term roadmap for FVON-Bahamas. 	
Gaps and Challenges	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance: Lack of a Capacity Building Subcommittee with a clear scope and objectives. Rejected IAPSO proposal for the development of capacity building documentation. No representation from Central or South America, Africa, or the Pacific Islands on the Steering Committee. 	

- **Expansion in Key Regions:** Lack of rigorous, reliable protocols for implementing FVON in new regions to ensure equity and sustainability. Little to no FVON presence in South America, West Africa, and Asia. Uncertainties around navigating potential legal challenges in new areas.
- **Knowledge Sharing:** Lack of documentation to introduce technology and methods to new partners. Need for a clear FVON menu of options and proposal templates to build capacity in regions with few resources.

Pillar 5: Global Coordination & Collaboration

Pillar Description	Governance
Achieving global change requires strategic engagement with key stakeholders across national, regional, and global levels.	Secretariat Steering Committee
Key Achievements	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance: FVON defined its Strategy and governance structure, informed by research interviews into existing ocean observing networks. Steering Committee and Secretariat established with defined Terms of Reference and objectives related to global networking, among other activities. Data Management Subcommittee works closely with OceanOPS. • Targeted Outreach: Attendance and presentations at 14 international conferences and events such as the UN Ocean Conference, BEFF, OOC, GCFI, OCG, CoastPredict GA, and others. FVON worked closely with OCG leadership at these events to advance conversations around new pilots in India, Africa, and the Caribbean. • Key Partnerships: FVON is an endorsed emerging network of GOOS (featured in the GOOS Annual Report 2025) and an Action of the UN Decade. CoastPredict and IOCARIBE advocating for the implementation of FVON across the Caribbean. GOOS and SAFET co-hosted the FVON webinar series. OceanOPS presented at the North Atlantic Arc Workshop, and FVON is involved in the OceanOPS 10,000 Ships Initiative. 	
Gaps and Challenges	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance: Limited attendance at industry- or policy-focused events due to largely scientific governance expertise and opportunities. • Targeted Outreach: Lack of success in outreach to FAO and other target organizations outside of OCG and CoastPredict. • Key Partnerships: FVON is not yet a mature network of GOOS. Global forecasting efforts largely exclude the integration of subsurface observations. 	

Pillar 6: Financial Innovation

Pillar Description	Governance
FVON promotes opportunities for financial innovation while maintaining scientific rigor with its broad consortium of public and private entities.	Financial Innovation Subcommittee
Key Achievements	

- **Governance:** Financial Innovation Subcommittee established with a clear strategy and regular meetings throughout the year. Several discussions held with GOOS and EDF representatives for broad strategic planning.
- **Funding:** Proposals submitted for the North Atlantic Arc, coral restoration, communications and outreach, and other objectives. Initial conceptual revenue models were defined and then developed with feedback from the Steering Committee and community.
- **Innovation:** Initial research conducted into the ocean data marketplace and economic tools to overcome market shortcomings, leading into the development of a data market blueprint. Research conducted into various blue economy industries and the existing funding mechanisms supporting ocean observing networks.

Gaps and Challenges

- **Governance:** Lack of a legal entity type or host institution, delaying trial of the revenue model. Overall inertia to disrupt the current funding environment.
- **Funding:** Continued dependence on philanthropic funding without diverse revenue streams. Secretariat capacity at risk beyond July 2026.
- **Innovation:** Delays from best practice development to set endorsement standards for FVON service providers under the proposed revenue model.

Strategic Implications

P1: QUALITY DATA

- **Governance:** Encourage and enforce active participation, particularly for creating consensus around best practices and carrying out sensor study activities. Prioritize funding for ongoing data management (hosting, maintenance, support, and development) and sensor study (open access publication, shipping and handling) costs. Formalize the Best Practices Subcommittee following the completion of Phase 2 of the sensor study.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Improve diversity of representation in FVON communications. Integrate feedback from participating manufacturers in the cruise report. Consider formalizing a technical advisory group in FVON for consistent communication and to support mutual benefits for sensor providers participating in FVON.
- **Quality Assurance:** Finalize the joint Phase 1 Cruise Report, formalize the data analysis framework, and publish the results on Zenodo, GitHub, and in a peer-reviewed journal. Initiate Phase 2 testing.
- **Quality Control:** Finalize QC documentation and ensure its practicality and usability across programs. Agree on cast parsing standards to consistently split casts into three phases: profiling down, fishing, and profiling up.
- **Metadata and Interoperability:** Create clear metadata and data management agreements. Finalize metadata standards, including naming conventions and consistent identifiers. Create a scalable workflow to assign WMO/WIGOS IDs to any interested program.
- **Data Sharing:** Stand up an endpoint where users can access open FVON datasets after QC. Decide on data architecture: a central FVON storage model or distributed storage managed by each program.

P2: MUTUAL BENEFITS

- **Industry Benefits:** Prioritize close collaborations with the private sector to develop economic proof points of data value. All new pilots should instill value return mechanisms for fishers that are not reliant on stipends alone.

- **Scientific Benefits:** Establish the Data Modeling Subcommittee and engage scientific partners in institutions worldwide. Use new FVON data streams (such as the North Atlantic) to drive progress.
- **Political Benefits:** Dedicate efforts into contributions toward global science and policy agendas. Institutionalize co-design frameworks for new regions in partnership with political actors.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Conduct early outreach for the second North Atlantic Arc workshop to ensure fishers are in attendance and help inform second wave of deployments.

P3: GLOBAL ADVOCACY

- **Governance:** Prioritize Secretariat capacity beyond July 2026. Encourage meaningful progress on communications materials that last beyond summer 2026.
- **Communications Channels:** Maintain the FVON newsletter and prioritize LinkedIn with a clear content mix with documents and short videos tied to milestones and key project reports, with features on key partners and/or sites to maintain reach. Lean into Instagram for reels and streamline Twitter and Facebook activity. Make social media activity more regular and amplified in scientific, political, and industry circles.
- **Projects:** Outsource or bolster Secretariat capacity for dedicated communications projects, such as the FVON webinar. Continue to utilize engagement with partners like GOOS and SAFET for support. Consider partnering with industry or government partners on a project.

P4: INCLUSIVITY

- **Governance:** Prioritize an in-person meeting and funding for this work, using the IAPSO proposal as a baseline and coordinating around well-attended conferences. Elevate program leads in underrepresented regions to stronger leadership positions, including Steering Committee membership. Develop metrics to quantify impact.
- **Expansion in Key Regions:** Target outreach for MC membership to strengthen FVON focal points in key regions. Continue working with IOCARIBE and other international partners to develop pathways for implementing FVON, tailored to underrepresented regions and aligned with UN Decade ocean literacy principles.
- **Knowledge Sharing:** Create practical, culturally-aware guidance for engagement with commercial fishing operators, artisanal and Indigenous fishers, communities in the Global South, and other partners. Include data informatics options and decision trees to build capacity in ocean data management, with options ranging from in-house to fully outsourced options. Publish guidelines and case studies from existing programs.
- **Sustainability:** Prioritize capacity building documentation, being considerate not to expand beyond what FVON is capable of maintaining. Develop health metrics to monitor sustainability risk of different pilots and programs, along with intervention strategies.

P5: GLOBAL COORDINATION & COLLABORATION

- **Governance:** Integrate non-scientific leadership in the Steering Committee. Institutionalize key stakeholders into FVON governance as advisory bodies and vice versa.
- **Targeted Outreach:** Target international and multilateral priorities through publications, presentations, and other communications materials.
- **Key Partnerships:** Investigate project proposals in collaboration with key organizations.

P6: FINANCIAL INNOVATION

- **Governance:** Continue testing and refining the Financial Innovation strategy. Prioritize a legal entity status to test the proposed revenue model. Engage with the private sector to develop proof of concept of ocean data. Consider formalizing an industry advisory group.
- **Funding:** Prioritize funding for the Secretariat and core operational activities. As a secondary priority, seek funding to run a pilot trial of the revenue model. Engage heavily with private and national partners and enter LOIs/MOUs to eventually diversify funding streams.
- **Innovation:** Create minimum standards for instrument and data management providers to enable the revenue model. Actively seek industry partnerships. Develop improved fisher-centric tools with demonstrated value for fisheries in line with the Financial Innovation strategy.

Assessment of 2025

The 2025 reporting period marked a foundational year for FVON, characterized by rapid organizational maturation, geographic expansion, and growing recognition within the global ocean observing community. FVON successfully transitioned from a loosely affiliated set of programs into a coordinated international network with defined governance, strategic pillars, and working mechanisms aligned with key international frameworks.

1. Governance

A foundational achievement of 2025 was the formalization of FVON's governance structure and strategic framework, including FVON's mission, theory of change, and organizational identity. This created the structured environment necessary to transition FVON from an informal collaboration into an emerging international network with articulated governance roles and decision-making. This is a critical step toward long-term institutional durability.

2. Standardization and Data Infrastructure

Significant progress was made toward standardization and interoperability, though full network-wide harmonization remains in development. Completion of Phase 1 of the sensor intercomparison study and deployment of shared FVON data access infrastructure are key advances that moved FVON beyond opportunistic data collection toward coordinated quality assurance processes. However, the absence of fully endorsed, network-wide best practices remains a primary barrier to reaching OCG maturity status.

3. Network Expansion and Global Advocacy

FVON demonstrated strong growth momentum by expanding from 489 to 744 vessels, entering into seven new countries, and establishing pilots in several under-observed regions. These achievements underscore the scalability of fishing-vessel-based observing systems when co-designed with local stakeholders and adapted to diverse contexts. FVON's presence across four ocean basins, presentations at 14 major conferences, and engagement with key partners (GOOS, CoastPredict, OceanOPS, etc.) position the network as a credible contributor to global observing priorities, particularly in coastal and shelf regions that remain under-sampled by traditional platforms. While geographic presence increased substantially, however, representation gaps remain in South America, Africa, and parts of Asia.

4. Financial Sustainability and Innovation

The Financial Innovation Subcommittee developed a strategy and draft revenue blueprint informed by interviews with stakeholders, comparative analysis of other OCG networks, and background research into blue economy industries. However, implementation is currently constrained by the absence of a legal entity, lack of formal endorsement standards for service providers, and continued reliance on short-term philanthropic and in-kind contributions. Critically, core FVON operations do not yet have secured, diversified revenue streams.

5. Communications

FVON significantly increased its visibility in 2025 through newsletters, webinars, short films, and sustained LinkedIn engagement. The two-part webinar series co-hosted by GOOS and SAFET demonstrated strong demand for dialogue around fisheries-based observing. However, communications capacity remains closely tied to Secretariat capacity, which lacks sustained coordination funding.

Overall, 2025 should be understood as a year of intentional groundwork. FVON demonstrated proof of concept at scale, validated demand from multi-sector stakeholders, and clarified the primary bottlenecks that must be addressed to enable long-term sustainability. The lessons learned during this period directly inform the strategic priorities for 2026.

Strategic Priorities for 2026

Building on the progress and lessons of 2025, FVON's priorities for 2026 focus on consolidation, standardization, and enablement. FVON should aim to shift from rapid formation toward sustained, repeatable, and scalable operations.

1. Formalize FVON as an Institution

Establishing a legal entity or host arrangement is the highest cross-cutting priority for 2026. This step is foundational for enabling financial innovation, entering formal agreements with partners, endorsing service providers, and sustaining Secretariat capacity. Without institutional status, progress across multiple pillars will remain constrained.

2. Advance Network-Wide Data Standards and Best Practices

FVON will prioritize completing and operationalizing unified QA/QC, metadata, and best practice frameworks. This includes finalizing outputs from the Sensor Intercomparison Study Phase 1, initiating Phase 2, formalizing a Best Practices Subcommittee, and aligning FVON standards with GOOS and OBPS endorsement pathways. Increased delivery of data to the GTS and consistent use of OceanOPS Passport metadata will be critical KPIs to monitor.

3. Strengthen Sustainability and Financial Pathways

FVON will focus on securing core funding for coordination and piloting a revenue model that supports both data collection and value return to participants. This includes developing minimum endorsement standards for instruments and data services, engaging private sector partners through proofs of concept, and pursuing partnerships with national institutions and industry actors.

4. Institutionalize Capacity Building and Equity-Driven Expansion

A dedicated Capacity Building Subcommittee will be established to document, standardize, and scale equitable implementation pathways. FVON will prioritize expansion in underrepresented regions—particularly South America, Africa, and Asia—while elevating leadership from these regions into governance roles. Practical guidance, templates, and decision frameworks will be developed to reduce barriers to participation.

5. Deepen Impact Through Data Use, Modeling, and Policy Engagement

FVON will strengthen the link between observations and outcomes by establishing a Data Modeling Subcommittee, expanding collaborations with forecasting centers and researchers, and translating scientific results into policy-relevant insights. Demonstrating tangible value across sectors will be critical for long-term adoption.

6. Maintain Strategic Communications and Global Advocacy

Communications efforts will focus on fewer, higher-impact products tied to concrete milestones, with continued emphasis on partner amplification. FVON will prioritize targeted visibility and outreach to key organizations, aligning with global priorities for climate resilience and sustainable fisheries.

Together, these priorities position 2026 as a pivotal year in which FVON continues to transition from an emerging network to a durable component of the Global Ocean Observing System—capable of sustained growth, consistent quality, and meaningful impact at scale.

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